

Biogas Reformation in Geothermal Wells

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Hydrogen energy and geological carbon retention using a biogas-geothermal wellbore reformation tool

Enhancing overall resource efficiency contributes significantly to energy security. Biogas serves as a critical energy asset within waste management by converting diverse organic wastes into higher-value products. Through the establishment of integrated partnerships, sector coupling underscores the synergies among geothermal energy, district heating, industry-related CO₂, urban biowaste, and agriculture. This innovative geothermal approach — applied to wellbore biogas reformation — facilitates hydrogen production alongside point-of-use geological carbon capture and storage (CCS). The Carbon Injection and Gasification Geothermal (CIGG) methodology offers a direct and effective pathway towards net zero by merging biogas reformation and carbon capture with low-grade district heat geothermal systems. This approach streamlines the hydrogen generation and CCS systems by eliminating unnecessary surface process steps, while incorporating reservoir heat storage and recovery, thereby reducing process energy consumption, costs, and material use, and results in an integrated, more energy efficient and sustainable solution.

To realise these synergies, a specialised wellbore tool for biogas (methane) reformation is under development, designed to leverage the natural properties of a geothermal reservoir formation and its fluids (i.e., heat storage, geothermal pressure, and temperature). The reformation's resulting hot CO₂ waste stream from this tool is injected into the reservoir, for heat storage and later recovery. This mitigates the reservoir rock's temperature depletion typically observed from long term production of geothermal power fluids. Moreover, this immediate, in situ downhole CO₂ capture will enable improved geothermal power efficiencies through enhanced heat recovery utilising the power fluid. As geothermal wells generally possess a lifespan of 15 to 25 years, integrating these processes bolsters long-term energy security. Overall, the CIGG process represents a mutually beneficial advancement for both energy sectors and environmental stewardship.

1. Biogas and Geothermal Sector Coupling

Biogas is considered carbon-neutral and is generated from a variety of sources (e.g., urban biowaste, landfill and agriculture). The methane (CH₄) content of biogas typically ranges from 45% to 75% by volume, with most of the remainder being carbon dioxide (CO₂). When biogas is upgraded, the biogenic CO₂ content is removed to create bio-methane (renewable natural gas). Some biogas operators capture this CO₂ content during the upgrading process for direct CO₂ sales (e.g., food or industry) or CCS. However, both these markets require high CO₂ purification from biogas upgraders with large process and transportation costs. Alternatively, upgrading operations often vent their CO₂ content to atmosphere. Furthermore, when the biomethane product is utilised by end-users in hard-to-abate sectors, this also typically leads to the release of its CO₂ into the atmosphere. Consequently, two distinct sets of CO₂ emissions can be associated with a biogas resource. Nevertheless, opportunities remain for the geothermal sector to further enhance the

environmental sustainability of biogenic biogas by optimising the energy generation and the carbon management of both types of biogenic CO₂, to create increased carbon trading volumes.

By directly eliminating the CO₂ emissions, and therefore who is accountable (i.e., Scope 1, 2, 3 or 4)¹, we can generate negative emissions for carbon trading, which is in line with the EU-wide Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA) which targets 50 Mt/yr CO₂ injection capacity by 2030 for permanent geological storage. Additionally, on July 2nd, 2025, the European Commission proposed a new EU climate target for 2040 of a 90% reduction in net greenhouse gas emissions compared to 1990 levels, with an interim target of between 66-72% by 2035, which aims to amend the European Climate Law of 55% by 2030. This was recently agreed on Nov 5th, 2025, by the 27 European Energy & Climate ministers. Complementary to this, the EU's Heating and Cooling Strategy (2016) aims to decarbonize heating and cooling by making it more sustainable while improving energy security. This emphasizes integrating renewable energy sources, enhancing energy efficiency in industry, promoting district heating and cooling networks, and the reuse of waste heat from industrial processes. In parallel, the EU Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM²) also aims to level the playing field between domestic and international carbon prices.

Biomethane, while biogenic, does not fully align with these strategies because it remains a carbon-based fuel that generates emissions. Therefore, developing an integrated energy process can help enhance energy generation together with carbon management systems, while supporting sustainability and energy security.

The transition to cleaner energy with lower costs and higher efficiencies faces several challenges. Energy Security will require continued commercial exploitation and growth of biogas energy reserves. How these resources are consumed, and how their associated carbon emissions are managed, is essential to both the speed and effectiveness of the green energy transition.

Both the biogas and geothermal sectors face sustainability challenges. Biogas is a carbon-based fuel (emitting CO₂) that may be subject to emerging climate restrictions, however its resources (e.g., agriculture, biomass, landfill gas and biowaste) all increase with population growth. Geothermal energy has commercial limitations due to high upfront capital costs (i.e., well costs are typically ~50% of geothermal project costs (IEA 2024)), and its scalability is currently restricted to <10% of the planet (i.e., to zones of shallow 'hot rock') (Duffield 2003). Reservoirs exceeding 150°C, at economic depths, are not widespread across the planet, however, shallower (< 2,000 m), sedimentary reservoirs below 60° C are more common.

To overcome these challenges, it is necessary to implement business strategies that are both energy and climate conscious and financially sustainable, while supporting the advancement of the circular economy and the green transition.

¹ **Scope 1: direct emissions** from own sources a company controls, like burning fuel in its vehicles or facilities, or fugitive emissions from leaks.

Scope 2: indirect emissions from purchased electricity, steam, heat, or cooling.

Scope 3: all other indirect emissions occurring in the company's upstream and downstream value chain, such as the transportation, distribution and use of its product.

Scope 4: avoided emissions outside a product's value chain as a result of a process used (e.g., improved energy efficiency or eliminating process steps).

² **CBAM** - a carbon price on imported goods like steel, cement, hydrogen, and fertilizers to prevent "carbon leakage". The charge is targeted any countries with less stringent climate policies, to ensure a comparable cost with embedded carbon emissions is included.

Our focus is to integrate both the geothermal and biogas sectors for a more immediate, direct and effective route to Net Zero, where the collaboration produces synergistic benefits, with one sector improving the commerciality of the other by omitting unnecessary or repeated process steps to improve overall energy efficiency. For biogas, geothermal wells provide a facility for hydrogen production, geological carbon capture (CCS) and heat storage. In contrast, for geothermal, biogas provides increased temperature and power output at greatly reduced well costs.

This synergy creates an economic pairing that enables geothermal energy's long-sought global geographic scalability; a powerful circular economic model between renewable gas and negative emission green hydrogen production, redefining how agricultural residues and organic waste streams can better contribute to clean energy systems with the aid of geothermal systems. Geothermal wells also create a secondary market for biogas production that may be constrained due to capacity limitations in local (biomethane) natural gas networks. This enables production growth in both sectors in tandem.

Integrating biogas reformation (hydrogen generation), CCS, geothermal, and district heating into one process (i.e., CIGG) is a breakthrough for Europe's net zero industry. It offers the first scalable integrated pathway to produce high-purity, negative-emission green hydrogen and achieve permanent, point-of-use CO₂ storage from renewable biogas, while creating artificially high reservoir fluid storage temperatures in shallow geothermal wells for power production and district heating. This change in energy generation, storage and carbon management enables geothermal, biogas, and agriculture sectors to become hydrogen, thermal battery and carbon capture leaders, taking advantage of existing licenses with fewer permitting barriers, less complex value chains and proven logistics.

To place biogas production into context, European biomethane production potential is estimated at 35 billion cubic meters per year by 2030, representing a multi-billion-euro market, with over 20,000 biogas plants currently in Europe (over 1,000 upgrading to biomethane) (EBA, 2023).

2. Optimizing Heat, Hydrogen and CCS for the Energy Transition

To realise the mutual benefits from sector coupling and to future-proof biogas production, the raw biogas composition is injected into the geothermal wells from surface. There is therefore no requirement for biogas upgrading (i.e., smaller surface plant area), reduced carbon footprint, and the sustainable exploitation of biogas as green hydrogen. As both sets of CO₂ emissions are captured from the biogenic, carbon-neutral, biogas source, there are no carbon emissions, and the geological CCS generates negative emissions. This process therefore allows full traceability and transparency of CO₂ capture.

To achieve this, a novel, low-capex, wellbore reformation tool is being developed. This patented process for methane reformation and separation radically shifts the generation of hydrogen from surface factories to deep in the wellbore (Gillick & Babaei, 2025). The reformation tool when placed in a geothermal well is accessible and controllable, using a design that is both modular and highly customizable. Methane reformation and subsequent hydrogen separation occurs inside the tool, where the wellbore depth provides naturally elevated input temperatures and pressures, creates a supercritical wellbore environment from deep wellbore compression, and improves heat exchange from wellbore geological insulation. The raw materials, machinery and disposal point are all in the well, with no requirement for surface CCS (i.e., separation, compression, injection, footprint, infrastructure and logistics).

When applied to the geothermal and biogas sectors, this wellbore technology enhances geothermal power efficiency while streamlining biogas processing. When the biogas is converted to generate hydrogen, the hot CO₂ waste stream is simultaneously injected, and carbon capture occurs in the geothermal reservoir. As this injection is a byproduct of the energy conversion process, the CCS is free and therefore sustainable. The hydrogen is produced to surface where it can either be exported or used on location to generate electricity (producing fresh water as a byproduct, for irrigation or domestic use).

If the CO₂ composition waste stream is injected into shallower formations, as it is hot (e.g., >150 °C), it artificially elevates the natural reservoir fluid temperature to the same temperatures as can be found in far deeper geothermal reservoirs. This ensures that there is no long-term thermal depletion of the reservoir rock (e.g., from injection of cold CO₂ or cooler recycled power fluid). Consequently, shallower sedimentary reservoirs can now be used to retain and recover heat to generate geothermal power, with less thermal loss during the production of fluids to surface. These better-quality sedimentary reservoirs have higher porosity and permeability, in contrast to the far deeper hard rocks that require expensive fracturing to create the geothermal reservoir and more wellbores to obtain economic flowrates for power production (i.e., typical commercial benchmarks of 80L/s can now be more easily achieved in the shallower sedimentary reservoirs). Closed loop well structures parallel to the injection wellbore can subsequently be used to provide geothermal heat recovery from the reservoir while still maintaining CCS, as there would only be thermal exchange with the reservoir and no fluid (CO₂) exchange.

Global geographic scalability is now possible, and these shallower, artificially hotter, geothermal power fluids can now also be used for electricity generation in addition to their original district heating. The heat for district heating now becomes a free byproduct of a far cheaper geothermal power system, with a lower requirement for, and better managed use of, heat pumps.

When incorporating reservoir fluid exchange, the hot injected waste fluids will enhance mineral extraction possibilities through, for example, better lithium chloride salt solubilities³, with the commercial benchmark for Lithium typical being 150-200 mg/L.

Alternatively, the methane reformation to hydrogen could be performed within a reformation tool placed at surface. The retained benefits would be machinery at surface (ease of maintenance), power fluid temps still boosted (from tool heat recovery at surface), H₂ and CO₂ separation still part of tool process, no thermal depletion of reservoir (if waste stream is still warmer than reservoir when injected). However, there will be a loss of process energy efficiency, higher energy consumption and heat loss with lower reservoir heat retention (less heat for the geothermal well to recover) and further disadvantages would be a requirement for CCS surface compression and injection, infrastructure and logistics requirements for the CO₂ disposal in the well, no supercritical tool environment (less energy efficiency), compression needed for surface generated hydrogen, and an overall larger surface plant footprint (more equipment).

When the methane reformation occurs in the tool, several endothermic and exothermic reactions occur simultaneously and are determined (i.e., Le Chatelier's Principle) by the pressure, temperature and relative concentrations, which are controlled by the biogas composition, air and water volumes injected from surface.

³ Lithium is extracted from geothermal wells as a dissolved salt (primarily lithium chloride) in the brine. The "dissolution temperature" for lithium salt solubility varies as a function of temperature, becoming more soluble as temperature rises (e.g., from 84.25 g/100 mL at 25 °C to 123.44 g/100 mL at 100 °C, a 46% increase).

Two main reactions determine the process.

For context, the total Danish national biogas production was 32 PJ/yr in 2023 (Danish Energistyrelsen, 2023). This is equivalent to approximately 93,000 tons/yr of negative emissions green H_2 and 1,500,000 tons/yr of CO_2 .

2.1 Geothermal Reservoir Heat Retention

Simulations were performed to test artificially elevated heat retention in the reservoir caused by the injected hot CO_2 composition waste stream from the reformer tool. The simulations were carried out using SLB's (formerly Schlumberger) industry standard compositional and thermal simulator, ECLIPSE E300. The simulator's capability to model various challenging cases of geothermal systems have been verified against more geothermal-tailored codes such as TOUGH series (Stacey & Williams, 2017).

The model was set up as a simplified version of a homogeneous geothermal layer (10 m), at depth 2,000 m TVD, with the geothermal well in the middle of a cylinder of 400 m radius. The initial temperature and pressure of the geothermal reservoir were set at 65 °C and 200 bar. To replicate open boundaries of the reservoir, an analytic aquifer (of same temperature and pressure of the geothermal reservoir) was attached to the outside boundaries. The compositional model takes care of brine in both vapour and liquid forms, with properties such as steam energy and enthalpy, steam and water density taken from the International Association for the Properties of Water and Steam (IAPWS-IF97) by using keyword THSTT97 in ECLIPSE E300.

The reservoir was discretized into 10 layers in vertical direction and 40 equal width rings in the radial direction. Permeability in the lateral direction was set at 1,000 mD with 100 mD in the vertical direction. The reservoir formation porosity is 20%, rock heat capacity is 2,500 kJ/m³/K, with the thermal conductivity of the rock 10 watt/m-C (Robertson, 1988). Liquid and Gas phase thermal conductivities are 0.7 and 0.047 watt/m-C, respectively. The reservoir was initialized with constant temperature and pressure, and the well is assumed to be perforated over the entire vertical interval of 10 m. The salinity of brine is set to 100 k ppm. The relative permeabilities of liquid water and vapour (gas) are provided in Figure 1. The equations solved are typical of two phase compositional thermal simulators, The thermal option runs in fully implicit mode in ECLIPSE E300. The thermal model for the steam injection should use a dummy dead-oil phase, so that the gas phase consists only of steam. For the compositional simulation between the phases, K-values (equilibrium ratios) of water are needed to determine the water partitioning into liquid and steam phases. The K-values are defined through the following equation:

$$K_{ww} = \frac{P_b(T)}{P}$$

Where $P_b(T)$ is the saturation pressure as a function of temperature. By using THSTT97 keyword, $P_b(T)$ is calculated from an analytical formulation as detailed in IAPWS-IF97.

Fig. 1: The relative permeabilities of liquid water and vapour (gas) used within the thermal simulation.

We simulated 6 cases for the CO₂ composition waste stream reservoir injection from the tool using a lower and upper bound for the flow rates, at three separate disposal temperatures. The upper (70 kg/s) bound flow rate was chosen to reflect typical commercial benchmarks quoted (IEA, 2024), while the lower (10 kg/s) bound was chosen to reflect those flow rates typically achieved from fractured wellbores in hard rock or deep reservoirs. Similarly, the waste stream injection temperatures were chosen to represent alternative exhaust temperatures from the tool, after the tool's methane reformation heat recovery module.

In reality, we would not aim to inject the CO₂ waste stream at any temperature higher than ~200 deg C, in order to optimise the tool's hydrogen generation (from low temperature Water Gas Shift reaction) and separation. This maximum of ~200 deg C also helps to optimise surface geothermal power generation (Hamm, 2025). We would then look to identify a suitable & competent sedimentary reservoir, with cap rock, at the shallowest depth available in that area (below ~1,000 m TVD).

- 10 kg/s of steam at 100 °C
- 10 kg/s of steam at 150 °C
- 10 kg/s of steam at 200 °C
- 70 kg/s of steam at 100 °C
- 70 kg/s of steam at 150 °C
- 70 kg/s of steam at 200 °C

Injections were simulated for 1 year, followed by 1-year post-injection monitoring. The simulator outputs the temperature of the reservoir fluid at the top of the reservoir at the injection well grid block, as well as at the heat recovery well (which is placed 100 m away from the injection well).

Fig 2 shows that after the first ~100 days there is no significant difference in the formation fluid temperature in the near wellbore area resulting from the lower and upper injection flow rates. It can be seen that very little reservoir fluid heat loss occurs at this location during the subsequent 1-yr shut-in period.

Fig. 2: The thermal simulation results at the CO₂ composition waste stream injection wellbore (top perforation), with injection stopped after 365 days.

Fig. 3: The thermal simulation results at the heat recovery wellbore, 100 m away, with injection stopped after 365 days.

Fig 3 clearly illustrates the benefit of using shallow sedimentary reservoirs with high permeability, that allow higher injection flowrates. The higher volume flow rates of the hot waste stream allow deeper reservoir fluid penetration to be achieved over the 1-year injection period. This, in turn,

provides a longer heat retention in the reservoir, after shut-in, around the 100 m heat recovery well, at full injection temperature. For high flow rates it can be seen that after shut-in very little reservoir fluid heat loss occurs over this 100 m well separation, and so very high efficiencies or better heat battery performance can be achieved at 70 kg/s. The higher flowrate also permits the potential for much earlier shut-in. For example, after only 100 days at 70 kg/s the thermal battery benefits are seen at the 100 m wellbore, whereas at 10 kg/s the fluid temperature is only marginally above the original geothermal reservoir temperature. For the lower flow rates, full injection temperature is not reached at the 100 m well after 1-yr, and subsequent heat loss to the formation fluids starts to occur immediately, as the cold front is much closer to the 100 m wellbore.

2.2 Geothermal-Biogas: Project Economics

Biogas operators can use this CIGG process to optimise their business models, by reducing capital and operational expenditure (streamlining processes), mitigating operational risks (e.g., calorific value discrepancy and natural gas network accessibility which cause flaring), and maximising available subsidy opportunities (increasing production). Expanding into new markets can further increase production volumes (lowering unit costs), and product value can be increased by prioritising hydrogen over biomethane, which also facilitates compliance with carbon taxation frameworks.

This CIGG coupling of geothermal and biogas produces a 'behind-the-meter' independence which can decentralize hydrogen and power production. This moves it closer to local biogas producing farming clusters, where energy and water requirements are better serviced, with the option to feed excess power into the national grid or hydrogen into the network.

These value drivers and savings create a commercial integration where the total is greater than the sum of its parts. This leads to enhanced revenue streams through the improved commerciality of biogas and geothermal collaborations, and full global geographic scalability is now possible (creating an economic co-dependency). Key value drivers include the benefits of shallower and fewer geothermal wells, reservoir heat retention and recovery, integrated CCS and the removal of biogas upgrading Capex and Opex. Enhanced Revenue streams are.

- Sales: Biogas / digestate (as eco-fertilizer) / Green Hydrogen / Electricity / Water
- Subsidies: Biogas production, Green-Hydrogen, Biogenic CO₂
- Negative Emissions (CCS) as Carbon Trading
- Geothermal incentives: feed-in tariffs
- Enhanced Power generation with District Heating
- Hot waste injection enables a 150 °C reservoir temperature commercial benchmark in shallower, better-quality reservoir use, that can produce higher flowrates (i.e., more power) to achieve the commercial benchmark of 80 L/s
- Secondary biogas market (as hydrogen) removes biogas production constraints

Savings from eliminated process steps, reduced process energy, and Capex and Opex costs

- No upgrade for biogas to biomethane
- 100% Carbon Capture, as a free, sustainable biproduct
- Offset District Heating costs as a free biproduct of power generation
- Navigate CO₂ Taxation more effectively
- No compression and transportation to off-site storage for greenhouse gases (GHG)
- Shallower geothermal wells lower well costs and allow simpler well design and well construction using cheaper, standard oil and gas industry well construction tools (without high-temperature, high-pressure or hard rock tool technology development delays)

- An integrated process means less process steps, better process efficiencies and less process energy consumption

3. Conclusion

The global energy transition is being held back by a dichotomy; a challenging geo-political environment around carbon-based fuels on the one hand, and the difficult financial metrics around renewables on the other.

By integrating geothermal energy with biogas, this CIGG process accelerates the clean energy transition and creates a sustainable, environmentally positive energy chain. It forms a circular, green economy that promotes climate beneficial hydrogen with integrated heat retention-recovery and CCS to grow geothermal and biogas markets in tandem. It changes how we use geothermal and biogas energy assets, infrastructure and workforce (human capital) and adapts existing energy generation to incentivize biogenic green hydrogen production. It decarbonizes industry and domestic energy using hydrogen, and generates hydrogen supply close to market, enabling the secure decentralization of power production in a 'behind-the-meter' approach to electric power generation. This decentralization will also reduce national power grid upgrade requirements. Decarbonizing methane in the wellbore will improve energy security by creating a secondary biogas market, increasing biogas production, leading to an increase in green hydrogen volumes, with wells capturing the carbon at point-of-use.

Promoting local, sustainable carbon capture, upstream, minimizes the huge expense (and subsidies) of CCS infrastructures for greenhouse gas transportation downstream to individual CO₂ capture points. Coupling Biogas, Hydrogen, Heat Retention and Recovery, Carbon Management, Geothermal and District Heating improves climate, commerciality, energy efficiency and energy security.

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